

HALF-YEARLY ABSTRACT
OF THE
MEDICAL SCIENCES.
JANUARY—JUNE,
1848.

LIST OF BRITISH AND FOREIGN PERIODICALS REFERRED TO IN
THE "HALF-YEARLY ABSTRACT."

BRITISH.

British and Foreign Medico-Chirurgical Review.
Medico-Chirurgical Transactions.
Edinburgh Medical and Surgical Journal.
London and Edinburgh Monthly Journal.
Dublin Quarterly Journal of the Medical Sciences.
Lancet.
Medical Gazette.
Provincial Medical Journal.
Medical Times.
Dublin Medical Press.
Bell's Pharmaceutical Journal.
Guy's Hospital Reports.
Chemical Gazette.
Chemist.
British Record of Obstetrical Medicine and Surgery.

AMERICAN.

American Journal of the Medical Sciences.
" " *of Science and Art.*
Philadelphia Medical Examiner.
New York Journal of Medicine.
Boston Medical and Surgical Journal.
Southern Medical and Surgical Journal.
British American Journ. of Med. Science.

FRENCH.

Annales de Chirurgie.
" *d'Hygiène.*
" *de Chimie et de Pharmacie.*
" *des Maladies de la Peau.*
" *Thérapeutique.*
Archives Générales de Médecine.
Bulletin des Académies.
Encyclographie Médicale.
" *des Sciences Médicales.*
Journal des Connaissances Médico-Chirurgicales.
Gazette des Hôpitaux.
" *Médicale.*
Journal de Chirurgie de M. Malgaigne.
Revue Médicale.
Journal de Chimie Médicale.
Journal de Chimie et de Pharmacie.

GERMAN.

Schmidt's Jahrbücher.
Zeitschrift für de Gesammte Medicin.
Muller's Archiv. für Anatomie, &c.
Liebig's Annalen der Chemie und Pharmacie.
Canstatt's Jahresbericht.
Buchner's Repertorium.
Haller's Archives für Physiolog. und Patholog. Chemie.
Casper's Wochenschrift.
Poggendorf's Annalen.

N. B.—Every periodical here specified is consulted directly by the Editor and his coadjutors.

THE
HALF-YEARLY ABSTRACT

OF THE
MEDICAL SCIENCES:

BEING

A PRACTICAL AND ANALYTICAL DIGEST OF THE CONTENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL
BRITISH AND CONTINENTAL MEDICAL WORKS PUBLISHED
IN THE PRECEDING SIX MONTHS.

TOGETHER WITH

A SERIES OF CRITICAL REPORTS ON THE PROGRESS OF MEDICINE AND THE
COLLATERAL SCIENCES DURING THE SAME PERIOD.

EDITED BY

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Apparatu nobis opus est, et rebus exquisitis undique et collectis, arcessitis, comportatis.—CICERO.

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The circulation in the head and upper extremities is more deranged in false than in true aneurism. The superficial veins become varicose; there is œdema of the face and neck, which arises from pressure on the veins.

ART. 28.—*On Pericarditis Scorbutica, and its Treatment by Paracentesis.*
By Dr. KYBER.

(*Oest. Med. Wochenschr.*, and *Monthly Journal*.)

The disease here described is found on the extreme northern coasts of Europe, where scurvy reigns endemically from spring to autumn, and affects almost exclusively the class of sailors, who are, of course, peculiarly exposed to all the causes of the scorbutic diathesis. This form of pericarditis appears to have been described by Cælius Aurelianus under the name of *morbus cardiacus*; but in more modern times has fallen into neglect, partly from the remoteness of the regions in which it prevails, and partly on account of the obscurity of the symptoms, and the deficiency of pathological observations. Dr. Kyber considers it as a very different disease, in its course and phenomena, from ordinary pericarditis. He thinks that its causes are the same as the scurvy, to which it is so closely allied; and remarks that the extent of its epidemic prevalence in a given year is always proportionate to the violence of scurvy in the same year. It seldom appears before February, attains its height about April, declines in summer, and disappears during autumn. It chiefly affects men from twenty-five to forty-two years of age; it has not been observed in women. A fourth of those affected are Russians, and three-fourths are Lettons (Lithuanians, &c.) and Esthonians, men mostly of a relaxed habit, and prone to hypochondriac and nostalgic affections. The external signs of scurvy are not always visible. In fatal cases the pericardium is found enormously distended, often measuring a foot in length, and containing three to eight, or even ten pounds, of dark red, or blackish opaque fluid, composed of serum and fibrin, with blood-corpuscles angular, and otherwise altered in form. The inner surface of the pericardium is covered with a coat of lymph, which is easily torn, reticulated on the free surface, of the colour of cinnamon. It can often be removed in layers, of which the palest and firmest are those attached directly to the membrane. The membrane itself is either injected, or stained with dark-coloured sugillations. On the part covering the heart, the lymph is often irregularly disposed in shreds, having a rugged or honeycomb appearance, and composed of bright red or yellow granules. The heart is diminished in size, and its substance is pale, flaccid, and easily torn. In cases where the fluid has been absorbed, adhesions are found between the layers of the pericardium. A similar exudation to that above described is frequently found in the pleura or peritoneum. The left lung is frequently much compressed by the distended pericardium, the right gorged with blood, or even inflamed.

The author describes the symptoms of this affection as occurring under two forms, acute and chronic; of which the former is commonly primary, the latter supervening secondarily on a catarrhal or rheumatic affection. The acute form begins with a sensation of coldness and prostration, oppression alternating with pain in the chest and epigastrium, rapid painless breathing, and decubitus on the left side; to these follows a discontented, gloomy condition, or complete apathy; with a pulse small, intermitting, or, when the effused fluid reaches two or three pounds, inappreciable. When the quantity of fluid is very large, the extremities are cold, the pupils dilated, the jugular veins distended, the expression exceedingly anxious; consciousness remains unaffected. The sound on percussion may be dull on the left front up to the clavicle; the heart's sounds distinct or inaudible, if the fluid be large in amount; if this be small, there may be friction-sound. The left side of the thorax is distended, and does not move freely; the lung on this side does not act; the right side, on the contrary, has puerile respiration. The epigastrium is protruded, and sensitive on pressure. In the acute form these symptoms may be developed in twelve hours; in the chronic the progress is longer, the danger to life less immediate; but the retrograde process of the disease, in case of amendment, is also much slower, and less satisfactory in its results.

In the treatment of this formidable affection, most of the remedies for ordinary

pericarditis are either inapplicable from the cachectic constitution of the patients, or, if applied, fail to accomplish any good purpose. The apparent certainty of a fatal issue in such cases induced the author to afford a chance of prolonged existence by paracentesis of the pericardium. This operation, however, he has not yet attempted, except in cases where death seemed impending, and where the fatal issue could only be postponed by a bold measure of immediate relief.

The operation performed by the author consists in the insertion of Schuh's trocar between the fourth and fifth ribs of the left side, close to the sternum, and passing it a little obliquely outwards, till the point is felt to enter the pericardium. The trocar is then withdrawn, and the fluid allowed to flow through the canula, which is apt to become blocked up by lymph, and in this case must be kept clear by a stilet, or probe. By this method both the pleura and the internal mammary artery are avoided. The operation is painless, except where it is necessary to remove, by the adaptation of a syringe, either fluid or air which has entered into the cavity. The immediate effects of it are, return of the pulse, removal of the anxiety and dyspnœa, and renewed animal heat, with comfort and cheerfulness of mind; at the same time the friction-sounds return, and the heart's sounds also become again appreciable. In the greater number of cases, life is merely protracted, as the fluid is again effused in a few weeks in as large a quantity as before, and becomes fatal. Nevertheless, in four cases the author has succeeded in accomplishing a radical cure. In three of these he administered, after the operation, the sulphate of quinine, which he recommends to be used in doses of six to fifteen grains every two or three hours, with the object of affecting favourably the capillary system, and preventing the renewed effusion of serum. The dissection of patients who, after an attack of this disease, have died of some other affection, show that when a radical cure takes place, it is through adhesion of the pericardial surfaces, which occurrence the author believes, however, to be much rarer in this than in other forms of pericarditis. He thinks that stimulating injections might possibly conduce to this favourable result, especially as it has appeared to him that the entrance of a certain quantity of air is productive of no bad result, but even seems to stimulate the membrane to a healing action.

In the four cases which were cured by paracentesis, the operation was only once performed. It was repeated (after the lapse of seventeen days) in one case only, and in this the result was unfavourable. He seems to think that if it were performed at an earlier period, it might be more frequently and permanently successful; but he has not thought himself justified in attempting this, having only operated in cases altogether desperate.

[The same disease has been described by Dr. Seidlitz, of St. Petersburg, under the title of Hemorrhagic Pericarditis. Vide Forbes's Brit. and For. Med. Rev., vol. i, p. 262.]

SECT. V.—DISEASES OF THE CHYLOPOIETIC SYSTEM.

ART. 29.—*Extract from Professor Andral's Lectures on General Pathology.—Semeiotics of the Digestive System.*

(*Medical Times.*)

1. *Signs furnished by the tongue.*—From the modifications brought on by disease in the circulation of the tongue, arise various changes of colour; for instance, a redness, which may be general or limited to the edges, apex, or centre of the organ; it may occupy only the papillæ, and at the same time its surface may be either dry or moist. The surface of the tongue may be smooth, as after desquamation of the epithelium; together with a change of colour, an alteration of size is sometimes observed; diminution, for instance, with redness, is indicative of disease of the stomach. The heat of the tongue may be increased, or may fall below its average standard; and in this latter case the organ acquires a purple hue, as in asphyxia and the blue period of cholera. Blood may also be extravasated on the tongue, and, drying up, leaves a black, fuliginous deposit on its surface. In chlorosis, on the contrary, the part is paler than during health.